

Title

An Exploration Of The Contexts Of Physical Activity That Best Support Positive Mental Health In Irish Adolescents

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Abstract

Physical activity is well recognised as a key risk factor for the management and prevention of mental ill-health. Physical activity guidelines are currently in place to best support optimal physical health in both young people and adults. Reference is made to the support of mental health through physical activity although no guidelines currently exist for the support or development of positive mental health or wellbeing. Previous investigations have shown mixed findings in relation to mental health in terms of overall volume, type and intensity of physical activity. The leisure-time life domain has shown the strongest associations with increased mental wellbeing and decreased depression and anxiety. Only one previous mixed-methods study has investigated the specific aspects of physical activity that are associated with positive mental wellbeing while no fully qualitative investigation has been undertaken. The majority of previous research has been conducted in adults although the focus on adolescents has increased in recent years. This study aims to identify the contexts of physical activity that best support positive mental wellbeing in Irish adolescents through photo elicitation techniques and semi-structured focus groups. A hybrid of inductive and deductive processes will be utilised to code, analyse and report key findings.

Keywords

Mental wellbeing; adolescent; physical activity; sport; team sport; qualitative

3 Main Highlights

- Physical activity is inherently good for both physical and mental health. Guidelines currently exist for the amount, type and intensity of activity for physical health but are still in need of development for optimal mental health.
- The context or life-domain of activity has a significant impact on mental health outcomes. The specific contexts that best support optimal mental health in adolescents are yet to be fully identified and refined.
- Design-thinking and photo-elicitation techniques have proven useful when encouraging adolescents to speak openly and honestly about their experiences with physical activity.

Introduction

Mental health disorders are the second leading cause of global burden of illness and growing rapidly (Kassebaum et al., 2017) with depression alone accounting for more than 44 million years lived with disability (Schuch et al., 2018). Given the breadth of mental health disorders and the accompanying individual and societal burdens, strategies that may reduce the onset of symptoms of anxiety and depression are urgently needed (Cuijpers et al., 2012). Physical activity is well recognised as a key risk factor for the management and prevention of mental ill-health, including anxiety and depression (Teychenne et al., 2020).

Physical activity guidelines have been developed and refined over several decades (see [table 1](#)). The original guidelines were published with a view to reducing the onset of cardiovascular disease-related mortality, and, subsequently, were developed to encompass other prevalent chronic conditions such as diabetes and cancer (Piercy & Troiano, 2018). Recommendations for physical health detail the volume, intensity and type of activity that should be undertaken by both adults and young people but make no reference to other contextual factors that have been shown to play a contributory role in the support or development of optimal mental health. Contextual factors across the lifespan include the life-domain that physical activity occurs in,

autonomous motivation, peer support, social interaction, access to green space, and progressions and achievements over time.

A clearer understanding of the bi-directional relationship between physical activity and mental health, or ill-health, may facilitate the delivery of successful interventions in future while also aiding the design and implementation of specific physical activity guidelines for mental health (Teychenne et al., 2020). The current evidence suggests there is a combination of both physiological and psychological factors involved in this relationship. The specific contribution of physiological and psychological factors is, as yet, unclear with a number of hypotheses currently proposed.

Table 1: Summary of the WHO Guidelines for physical activity and sedentary behaviour (Bull et al., 2020)

Group	Physical Activity	Sedentary Behaviour
<p>Children and adolescents (aged 5-17 years), including those living with disability</p>	<p>In children and adolescents, physical activity confers benefits for the following health outcomes; physical fitness (cardiorespiratory and muscular fitness), cardiometabolic health (blood pressure, dyslipidaemia, glucose and insulin resistance), bone health, cognitive outcomes (academic performance, executive function) and mental health (reduced symptoms of depression) and reduced adiposity.</p> <p>It is recommended that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Children and adolescents should do at least an average of 60 min/day of moderate-to-vigorous intensity, mostly aerobic, physical activity, across the week; ○ Vigorous-intensity aerobic activities, as well as those that strengthen muscle and bone should be incorporated at least 3 days a week. <p><i>Strong recommendation</i></p>	<p>In children and adolescents, higher amounts of sedentary behaviour are associated with detrimental effects on the following health outcomes: fitness and cardiometabolic health, adiposity, behavioural conduct/pro-social behaviour and sleep duration.</p> <p>It is recommended that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Children and adolescents should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary, particularly the amount of recreational screen time. <p><i>Strong recommendation</i></p>

Although the physical activity guidelines make reference to reducing the risk of depression and anxiety in adults and reducing the risk of depression in young people, the evidence behind these recommendations is nowhere near as strong as those for physical health (Biddle & Vergeer, 2020). It is also unclear if the same volume, type or intensity of activity is required for supporting positive mental health as for physical health. The majority of research, particularly reviews and meta-analyses, have been conducted in adult cohorts. Throughout this paper we draw on all of the available current evidence although there is a need for specific focus on adolescent cohorts in the future.

Volume of physical activity

A recent meta-analysis of 49 prospective cohort studies (Schuch et al. 2018) found those with higher volumes of physical activity had lower odds of developing depression across all ages (young people, working-age adults and elderly people), and this was robust across geographical regions around the world. The risk of developing depression was reduced by 22% in adults who achieved the minimum recommendations of 150 minutes per week (Schuch et al., 2018), although a protective effect against depression was also observed in those who achieved less than 150 minutes per week when compared to largely inactive individuals. This is in agreement with a number of systematic reviews who have shown that even low doses of physical activity are associated with a reduced likelihood of developing depression (Mammen & Faulkner, 2013). Another meta-analysis including 11 prospective cohort studies found that sedentary behaviour is associated with an increased risk of developing symptoms of depression at follow-up (relative risk = 1.14) (Zhai et al., 2015). This suggests the benefits of physical activity for the treatment and prevention of depression may be attainable at lower volumes of physical activity than the guidelines currently recommend, particularly when those most at risk are less likely to be sufficiently active (Vancampfort et al., 2017) and may prefer lighter forms of

physical activity (Fraser et al., 2015). Similar findings have been reported for anxiety as for depression. A meta-analysis of 13 unique prospective cohort studies found that people with higher volumes of self-reported physical activity were at reduced odds of developing anxiety (Schuch et al., 2019). A further systematic review and meta-analysis of 13 prospective cohort studies that focused solely on those with a clinical diagnosis also found that any anxiety disorder were significantly lower after physical activity exposure when followed up at least 1 year later (McDowell et al., 2019). It is clear that increased volumes of physical activity are associated with lower levels of depression and anxiety although exactly how much is currently unclear. The available evidence suggests it is below the current guidelines for physical health as set out by the World Health Organisation (2010).

Type of physical activity

As stated in the current guidelines for health (Bull et al., 2020), adults should perform muscle-strengthening activities involving major muscle groups on 2 or more days per week while children and adolescents should perform vigorous-intensity activities that strengthen muscle and bone, at least 3 times per week (World Health Organisation, 2010). Most prospective studies investigating the impact physical activity has on mental health have largely focused on establishing a dose-response relationship although the exact dose required has not yet been determined. Little relevance has been paid to the type or mode of physical activity (Mammen & Faulkner, 2013; Schuch et al., 2013) until recently with the primary focus on aerobic type exercise. Meta-analytic evidence has found that resistance training improves symptoms of both depression and anxiety (Gordon et al., 2017; Gordon et al., 2018) in adults regardless of health status, total prescribed resistance training, or significant improvements in strength. Comparisons between aerobic exercise only and resistance exercise only found no significant difference (Schuch et al., 2016) in the effect of reduced symptoms of depression. Furthermore, an analysis of 17,839 adults who adhere to both the aerobic and muscle strengthening

guidelines were at the lowest risk of developing symptoms of depression, compared to those who adhere to only one guideline (either aerobic or muscle-strengthening activities) (Bennie et al., 2019) while another analysis of 5,100 females found those who met the aerobic and resistance training guidelines had a stronger association with lowered risk of symptoms of both depression and anxiety than only meeting the aerobic recommendations (Ofstedal et al., 2019). These studies suggest a synergistic relationship between aerobic physical activity and resistance training in terms of mental health benefits. It could be argued that those who engage in both aerobic physical activity and resistance training have a greater volume of total time in activity and thus accumulate more MET-minutes, although the effectiveness of resistance training in reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression has been demonstrated in experimental studies (Gordon et al., 2020).

Intensity of physical activity

The modes of exercise outlined in the previous section vary in intensity when compared to each other while cardiorespiratory endurance and resistance exercises can often be performed at a variety of intensities. The current guidelines for physical health can be met through either moderate or vigorous intensity exercise with vigorous intensity exercise appearing to be more time efficient. The effect that intensity of physical activity may play on mental health outcomes is, as yet, unclear although initial evidence shows both positive and null effects. Studies involving high intensity interval training have shown some improvements in psychological wellbeing among adolescents (Costigan et al., 2016) although null effects were found for anxiety in young adults (Eather et al., 2019). There is currently no evidence to suggest that high intensity interval training has negative impacts on mental health, although it may be associated with more negative affective states during participation (Teychenne et al., 2020), compared to lower-intensity exercise, which can predict drop-out and therefore reduce the likelihood of meeting physical activity guidelines (Biddle & Batterham, 2015). The strenuous nature of high

intensity interval training may also undermine competence (Biddle & Batterham, 2015), particularly for people in the lowest activity groups, and thus have negative knock-on psychological effects to those already in a high risk category.

Context of physical activity

When examining the roles of volume, intensity and type of exercise on mental health there is inconclusive evidence regarding any one specific recommendation that can be made. More exercise is better but we may not need to meet the current physical activity guidelines for physical health. Benefits were found when engaging in aerobic and resistance exercise, with some of the largest benefits observed in those who engaged in a combination of more than one form of exercise (Oftedal et al., 2019). Varying intensities also showed inconsistent results with both high and low levels of intensity conferring similar benefits. Recent research has shifted from volume, intensity and type of physical activity to the context or life-domain through which it is engaged in. The guidelines for health do not distinguish between where physical activity is undertaken and state that “*physical activity includes recreational or leisure-time physical activity, transportation (e.g. walking or cycling), occupational (i.e. work), household chores, play, games, sports or planned exercise, in the context of daily, family, and community activities*”. The variety of life-domains outlined suggest the context of physical activity is largely irrelevant and benefits to physical health from physical activity are predominantly physiological. As the aforementioned mechanisms of physical activity and wellbeing suggest combinations of both physiological and psychological processes, it gives us reason to believe the domain of physical activity plays a significant role for the prevention of mental ill-health and the promotion of positive mental health. A meta-analysis of domain-specific physical activity and associations with mental health found leisure-time physical activity and active travel to be positively associated with mental health while leisure-time

physical activity and school sport were inversely associated with mental ill-health (White et al., 2017). However, physical activity was not consistently associated with lower mental ill-health across domains as work-related physical activity was positively associated with mental ill-health while household chores and physical education had no relationship with mental health or mental ill-health (White et al., 2017). Interestingly, the positive association observed between active travel and mental health was primarily in adults while studies involving adolescents showed null and negative associations between active travel and mental health (White et al., 2018). This highlights the need to investigate the varying impacts of physical activity in adolescents as distinct from adult cohorts. Life-domain was found to significantly moderate the relationship with physical activity and mental ill-health, thus highlighting the need to investigate the most appropriate contexts of physical activity that best support mental health and wellbeing.

A sub-domain of leisure-time physical activity, with a growing body of research, is the impact of sport on mental health outcomes. Azstalos et al., (2009) found that participation in sports, and no other form of physical activity was consistently associated with significantly less stress and distress. A recent meta-analysis also found that symptoms of anxiety and depression were significantly lower among sport-involved adolescents than in those not involved in sport (Panza et al., 2020). Recent cross-sectional analyses found sport to have a significant protective effect against symptoms of depression and anxiety in adolescents (McMahon et al., 2017; Murphy et al., 2020). It is therefore arguable that sports participation may represent effective preventive and intervention strategies against stress and distress, both leading causes of symptoms of anxiety and depression.

The current literature suggests no specific volume, intensity or type of physical activity is most appropriate for the support of positive mental health and wellbeing of adolescents, although the context of physical activity appears to play a significant role (White et al., 2017; Teychenne

et al., 2020). Physical activity contexts can include a number of factors such as motivation for exercise, who you're exercising with, where you're exercising, and opportunities for achievement and progression. The specific contexts of physical activity that contribute to positive mental health and wellbeing have, as yet, been unidentified by adolescents themselves and require greater investigation as to why they play a significant role. Exploring the thoughts and experiences of active and sport playing adolescents themselves will help to identify the key factors that support, and may develop, positive mental health and wellbeing to inform future physical activity provisions.

Research Problem

Increasing physical activity in and of itself is not likely to be worthwhile in terms of reducing the prevalence of mental ill-health, as individuals with occupations that involve higher amounts of physical activity, are more likely to experience mental ill-health. This suggests physical activity is not automatically associated with greater mental health and reduced mental ill-health, and that contextual factors are crucial to such relationships (White et al., 2017). Current evidence suggests that leisure-time physical activity is likely to be an optimal domain to promote mental health and prevent mental ill-health. Gaining knowledge of the specific factors that mediate or moderate the relationship between physical activity and mental health, particularly through the leisure-time domain, will help lead to the development of contextually tailored interventions and physical activity guidelines, and improve the effectiveness of physical activity as a prevention and treatment method. Including the adolescent voice in defining what wellbeing is and how physical activity can positively impact wellbeing will help to design physical activity opportunities in the future that both help to develop positive mental and physical health but also meet the needs of adolescents themselves.

Aim & Objectives

Key Aim: Explore which contexts of physical activity have the strongest associations with wellbeing and mental health in Irish adolescents

Objectives:

- Identify aspects of leisure time physical activity that best support positive mental health.
- Explore potential differences in physical activity experiences between males and females to identify if they impact differently on positive mental health.
- Identify the aspects of team sport that offer a “protective effect” against symptoms of mental ill-health.

Methods

The empirical data will be collected over a 4-6-week period and qualitative data collection methods will be used (Bryman, 2016); specifically focus groups, artefacts, design thinking tools, and researchers’ reflective journal. Artefacts and design thinking tools will be employed to aid in the engagement of youths in the focus groups (Cuthbert, 2018). Inclusion of the adolescent voice in physical activity research has increased recently as adolescents try to express the meaning physical activity holds for them and provides an opportunity to contextualise such understandings within their everyday physical and social worlds (Patton & Parker, 2013; Macdonald et al., 2005).

Photo-elicitation interviews

Photographs can prompt and support both reviewing and reflecting on experiences (Lapenta, 2011) as a form of reflexive analysis and have previously been used successfully in education contexts (Miles & Kaplan, 2005). Photos can act as a ‘cue’, a form of prompt, to aid memory and reflection while also aiding in the emergence of new insights (Pope, 2010). A main goal of photo-elicitation is to create critical dialogue and knowledge about important issues through discussion of photographs (Patton & Parker, 2013). Allowing participants to choose a photo

themselves will encourage greater authentic participation (Rudduck & McIntyre, 2007) by allowing them to engage in conversations that allow for their decision making, investment and participation around issues of direct interest to their lives and lived experiences (Enright & O'Sullivan, 2012). Participatory research methods, where the participants source the photos themselves, facilitate finding of their own language to articulate what they know, and help them put words to their ideas and feelings and share understandings of their worlds, thereby giving participants more control over the research process (Enright & O'Sullivan, 2012). Allowing participants to construct meaning of their lived experiences in physical education or sporting contexts in school and the community creates authentic involvement in the research enterprise. Engaging young people as co-researchers (Enright & O'Sullivan, 2012) increases engagement and allows them to play a more central role in shaping their own and others' experiences around physical activity and sport.

Sampling and Participants

The research sample will consist of at least 3 schools, comprising of one all-male, one all-female and one mixed. The sample will be a purposive cohort from a larger quantitative study (Murphy et al., 2020) which sought to establish baseline data on physical activity and mental wellbeing in Irish adolescents. All schools (n = 14) who provided 100 or more participants will be invited to participate in this follow-up qualitative study. Final selection will be based on timetabling availability in the schools who show interest. The aim is to conduct 3 focus groups in each school. One group will be comprised of participants who engage in team sport. One will be comprised of participants who identify as "active" but do not engage in a team sport. A third group will be comprised of students who do not identify as "active". Self-selection of groups based on activity will facilitate a focus on activity preferences and related decision-making and motivations pertaining to these activities. Diverse background experiences of participation in physical activity and sport may lead to a variety of insights and important

differences in how physical activity may impact positive mental health. Previous quantitative research has highlighted differences in mental wellbeing based on activity levels and engagement in team sport (McMahon et al., 2017; Murphy et al., 2020; Murphy et al., 2021). Allowing participants to speak with peers who have had similar experiences may allow them to create deeper meaning from these shared experiences.

Data Analysis

A hybrid process of inductive (data-driven) and deductive (theoretical) coding adapted predominantly from Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006) with influence from Braun and Clarke (2006), Boyatzis (1998) and Crabtree and Miller (1999) will be used to analyse data. Codes can be conducted “a priori”, based on prior research or theoretical perspectives, or created on preliminary scanning of the text with some initial codes refined and/or modified during the analysis process (Crabtree & Miller, 1999). Deductive analysis will draw on themes previously identified in a qualitative investigation of the perceived influence of adolescents’ motivation on relationships between domain-specific physical activity and positive and negative affect (White et al., 2018) and from self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 1978).

This approach will consist of seven stages:

1. Development of codebook from White et al., (2018), self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 1978), and a pilot study.
2. Code stratified sample of main data.
3. Broad reading and summarising of entire data set.
4. Code data using inductive and deductive codes.
5. Group codes to develop thematic map.
6. Review themes and use the data to check for internal and external homogeneity.
7. Define and name themes.

Stages 3-7 are broadly in alignment with Braun and Clarke's (2006) five step approach to thematic analysis who treated inductive and deductive approaches to coding as separate techniques. An integrated method of qualitative data analysis has previously been used in an Irish educational context to examine mathematical identity in students (Howard, Nic Mhuiri & O'Reilly, 2019).

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval has already been granted for the focus groups to take place both in person and online (via Zoom). A question guide will be submitted prior to any focus groups taking place. All recorded conversations will be transcribed and anonymised by the lead researcher (JM) within 4 weeks of the focus groups taking place. Digital recordings of the conversations will be stored in password protected files that can only be accessed by the lead researcher. All necessary attempts will be made to protect the identities of the participants and their schools. No individual participant or participating school will be named in subsequent publications or other areas of research dissemination. Ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of participants is important in encouraging the discussion of personal experiences and viewpoints during focus group interviews. Consent will be sought from the Principal of each school and submitted to the ethics committee before any students are recruited or briefed on the research project. Parental consent and participant assent will be sought through signed consent forms accompanying plain language statements before any interviews have begun. Participants are reminded that they can withdraw from the research process at any stage throughout the interview. Any photos containing images of people, or anything else that could identify someone, will be blurred in subsequent publications.

Conclusion

This hybrid of inductive and deductive methodology seeks to facilitate a thematic analysis incorporating the knowledge from previous work on adolescent perceptions of physical activity and wellbeing. Identifying the key aspects of contexts of physical activity that best support mental wellbeing in adolescents will help to design future interventions and ultimately inform physical activity guidelines in the future.

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